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Development of an anonymous online course feedback system for improving students' learning experience in engineering higher education

Erja Sipilä¹

University Lecturer

Laboratory of Electronics and Communications Engineering

Tampere University of Technology

Tampere, Finland

E-mail: erja.sipila@tut.fi

Sara Selänne

Research Assistant

Teaching and Learning Services

Tampere University of Technology

Tampere, Finland

E-mail: sara.selanne@tut.fi

Veli-Pekka Pyrhönen

Doctoral Student

Laboratory of Automation and Hydraulics

Tampere University of Technology

Tampere, Finland

E-mail: veli-pekka.pyrhonen@tut.fi

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¹ Corresponding Author

Erja Sipilä

erja.sipila@tut.fi

INTRODUCTION

The extremely rapid technical development together with global operational environment in engineering disciplines require that students of engineering in higher education learn effectively very complex issues in quite a short time. To enable students' effective learning, studies and teaching must be developed constantly. A systematic online course feedback system (OCFS) is one instrument for this. In this study, feedback refers to student feedback, which is provided by students to teachers, not e.g. teacher's response to students' assignments.

Feedback can be considered as a fundamentally important component of education [1] and many universities and other institutes of education use at least some kind of student feedback questionnaire to evaluate teaching [2,3]. The use of OCFSs is increasing, taking room from traditional pen and paper feedback [4]. Multiple different platforms and questionnaire types are used throughout the world, all of them having their own benefits and disadvantages. In Tampere University of Technology (TUT), Finland, there is an OCFS already in use, but it is about time to renew it. Hence, the time for both technical and content renewal is now in hand.

In this study, we present the results of a survey that was carried out in TUT to develop the anonymous OCFS to boost students' studies and learning experience in every possible way. Feedback of the current OCFS together with further development ideas were collected in TUT with teacher interviews and with an anonymous Webropol survey.

Course feedback gives, or can give, deeper insight into students' study experience. However, the course feedback is mainly used, at this point, to develop practical issues, like course scheduling and course materials. In this study, based on the survey, we present ideas for improving the collection and utilization of feedback from an OCFS in order to enhance students' learning experience in engineering higher education.

1 LEARNING AND COURSE FEEDBACK

Student feedback is important, because otherwise students' voice would not be heard by the teachers and other groups of interest, e. g. faculty, university, national and international education development forums. Traditionally the aim of student feedback has been to improve teaching [2]. However, this approach can take the focus away from where it should be: student learning. Teaching and learning are not always in positive relation to each other because the improved teaching does not necessary lead to improved learning. Often this causality takes place, but not always. Student learning is the ultimate goal for all universities and this is why student feedback should be more concentrated to student's learning instead of just evaluating teaching.

When thinking about learning, we must remember, that the learner, or in this case the university student, is responsible for his/her own learning and actions that enhance learning. Nobody else can do the learning for the student. However, when thinking about studying in a university, the student's learning experience can be supported by the teacher, and in this way student's learning can be enhanced.

It is also good to remember, that the learning experience does not have to be positive, e. g. fun or easy, to promote student's learning. Many times hard, difficult and time-consuming learning experiences are superior when it comes to student learning. However, in OCFS answers students very seldom want more of these time consuming and difficult tasks. Consequently, the teacher has a major responsibility to develop the courses, and in this way also students' learning experiences, in the direction which is beneficial to learning, even though the student feedback would indicate otherwise.

Therefore, teachers must choose case-by-case, whether they will attempt to make corrective adjustments based on the feedback received, or should they do something else, which will promote student's learning through student's improved learning experience.

1.1 The most suitable timing for course feedback

Student feedback can give the teacher great ideas to develop the learning experiences of students so that student's learning is also supported. However, this requires that the results of an OCFS are read and analysed carefully, and after this teacher can utilize the results to enhance the learning of students. Generally, student feedback considers learning events that have occurred in the past. The events have generated individual learning experiences, feelings and opinions among students, which influence on the nature of their course feedback. Sometimes some students base their feedback entirely on personal feelings and experiences, while others have more objective focus on their feedback without emotional components involved. However, feelings and emotions are of course an integral part of students learning experience, this should be kept in mind.

Nonetheless, often feedback attempts to influence on prospective actions so that some desired outcomes will be achieved in future. In this sense, student feedback collected at the end of the course implementation is problematic, because the respondents will not generally be participating in the forthcoming implementations. Therefore, usually nowadays actions taken by the teacher will only affect to future implementation, which will have new students with new needs and expectations that will likely differ from the needs and expectations of the students that previously attended the course. Therefore, it would make more sense, if course feedback would be collected earlier during the course so that attempts to make corrective actions would be effective for those who need them, the current students on the course.

Perhaps the best possibility would be real-time feedback, so that students could give feedback at any time, and as many times as they want during the course. Put to general terms, course feedback mechanism scheduled at the end of the course creates an undesirable situation: previously experienced unwanted features by current students will be attempted to remove proactively, in future, by teachers who must base their actions on reactive information from the past, and these actions will be targeted to students who did not observe these unwanted features.

2 CURRENT COURSE FEEDBACK SYSTEM IN TUT

A teacher can collect course feedback in many ways. The most widely used methods are probably pen-and-paper feedback and online feedback [5]. In general, one big question in OCFSs has been how to ensure adequate response rates [5]. The pen-and-paper feedback collection is traditionally done in classroom and urged by the teacher, but in the case of OCFS students answer to it usually outside classroom [5]. Traditionally the pen-and-paper feedback collecting method has gathered the highest response rates [5, 6]. However, the response rates of an OCFS can be extremely high if answering is compulsory for students.

TUT uses currently an OCFS. However, the technical platform behind it is coming to the end of its lifecycle, and it needs either massive improvement or total replacement. Hence, now is a perfect time to renew also the content of the OCFS in TUT. The aim of this renewal is to make the OCFS much better for students than the old OCFS was, especially so that students could have an insight into their learning when using it, in addition to giving traditional course feedback. This study does not concentrate on the technical platform of the OCFS.

Three numerical questions are the same and compulsory for each course in TUT in the current OCFS in TUT. A teacher cannot remove these compulsory questions even if he/she would try to do so. Feedback from all the courses in TUT can be studied and compared together with the compulsory questions, and TUT's teaching as a whole can be developed based on these answers.

In addition to compulsory questions, a course responsible teacher can add questions to his/her courses' questionnaires. The questions can be either numerical or open-ended. There is a question bank available in the OCFS, where the teacher can choose ready-made questions, or he/she can create new questions of his/her own.

The results of numerical questions are displayed as mode, median and average. The answers of open-ended questions are displayed as they have been written in the OCFS. One big disadvantage of the current system is that it does not provide any kind of figures or charts from the numerical results.

Answering the current OCFS is compulsory for all the students; otherwise the student does not have the course grade in his/her study record. The current OCFS does the checking, teacher has not to take care of this. The teacher gives the grades normally, but if a student has not given course feedback, the course grade does not appear in his/her study record. Because the course feedback is compulsory, there is a possibility for false answers from students. If a student just wants to get his/her grade to the record, the possibility for random answers, which are not anyhow related to the student's thoughts, is obvious. This is avoided by adding an "I do not want to give feedback" button to the questionnaire. A student can choose it, and then he/she can get the grade to the study record without distorting the feedback results. However, surprisingly few students choose this possibility. A vast majority of students really give course feedback using the OCFS.

3 METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In this study, the primary research data was collected using two sources of evidence: face-to-face interviews and an anonymous online questionnaire. The participants in this study are teachers from TUT and their participation was voluntary. Three teachers took part both in the interview and the questionnaire and this was taken into account when the data was analysed.

The teachers of TUT were informed about this study and the possibility to take part in the interviews through their email list. As a result, we received ten interviewees to participate in this study. The interviews took place in October 2017 and the research assistant of this study acted as the interviewer. After the interviews, the amount of ten interviewees proved to be a suitable sample size for this study because the saturation level was reached in the interview data.

The interview method was semi-structured, because we wanted that the respondents could have the possibility to steer the topic of the discussion to subjects that they considered important. The teachers were interviewed individually, and the interviews were carried out face-to-face. In order to analyse the interview data, the interviews were recorded with the consent of the participants and based on the recordings the research assistant wrote detailed notes.

The questionnaire was created after the interviews with an online survey tool called Webropol and it consisted of 11 questions, 6 of which were open-ended. The rest of the questions were in the form of statements and the response options were formed with a five stage Likert scale. The link to the questionnaire was sent to the teachers of

TUT through their email list and the questionnaire was open to replies for two weeks in November 2017. We received a total of 22 responses.

Both the interview and the questionnaire data were analysed with the help of qualitative content analysis. This means that the analysis involved the identification of common patterns within the responses. The questionnaire data was coded with different colours and the findings were compared with the findings of the interview data. We wanted to use two different sources of evidence because using multiple sources simultaneously is often considered to increase the reliability of qualitative research [7].

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from the teacher interviews and the Webropol-questionnaire can basically be divided into two categories: Technical issues and content issues. Both of these are strongly related to students' learning experience, but in different ways.

4.1 Technical issues

The results of this study indicate that the user experience of an OCFS is extremely important. The usability of the system has to be smooth, and the user interface (UI) has to be easy to use. In addition, the OCFS has to be technically compatible with mobile devices.

The use of an OCFS is part of the students' learning experience. If the UI and usability of OCFS are not in order, the students get frustrated and this possibly affects the collected feedback, leading to distorted course feedback. In addition, in the case of distorted feedback, the student cannot or may not use the OCFS as a tool for their own self-reflection in learning. If this happens, one of the big purposes of the OCFS is lost.

The results also show the importance of practical course arrangements. As an example, scheduling, classrooms and course materials must be well planned and carefully chosen to ensure the best possible learning experience for students. These practicalities can be easily asked in the OCFS, and these issues can be quite easily affected even during a course.

This leads to one result of this study, the OCFS should be real-time, meaning that the students can give feedback whenever they want and wherever they are. The real-time possibility to give feedback aids the students to use the OCFS as a system for their self-reflection as learners. In addition, the teacher can react to many issues immediately during the course, not just after it. These issues undoubtedly include practical issues like course material updating, but also issues related to e. g. the depth of handling the subject matter, and classroom time used to the course topics. However, the utilization of real-time feedback can be quite time-consuming for a teacher, but we think it is definitely worth it.

4.2 Content issues

The questions in the OCFS should be both numerical and open-ended. The numerical answers are easy to analyse with statistical methods, different kinds of characteristics and charts can be established based on them. However, the teachers in this study very strongly think that the open-ended questions give the most valuable course feedback. The students can show their ideas connected to teaching and learning processes [8]. Here are a couple of comments from the teacher interviews (translated from Finnish):

"The feedback gives insight to a student's daily grind."

"Qualitative feedback is more useful. This means open ended questions."

"Feedback makes the student think about his/her own learning process."

“Feedback is much used to develop course practicalities. However, it would be more rational to see, what is learned and what is not.”

With open-ended questions a teacher can follow student's thoughts, and this way the teacher can get a glimpse of the students' learning process. The teacher gets a sight to the students' different learning styles and strategies. The learning of students increases when the teacher knows students' different attitudes and responses to teaching and learning [9].

Based on these results the questions in an OCFS should be developed towards aiding students' learning. The idea of using an OCFS as a system for student's own self-reflection tool for learning is rising all the time. These kind of questions also help teachers to develop the courses so that the students learn better and they have learning experiences that improve their learning.

4.3 Other issues

In addition to the answers relates to students' learning and learning experience, a couple of points arose continuously in the data: answering to the OCFS should be compulsory for the students, and the students as well as the teachers need training how to give and receive constructive feedback. Now, with the current OCFS in use, a big problem with the university level questions is that they are close-ended in a way that the teacher cannot get the idea behind the student's feedback. The numerical results for e. g. a question like “Overall rating of the course and its implementation” do not tell what was good and what should be improved in a course. Furthermore, if a student writes e. g. “The course was bad”, the teacher does not know what needs most improving. Hence, the skill to give feedback so that it tells in more detail about the course, and learning on it, is essential.

5 SUMMARY

The main finding in this study is that course feedback system, no matter in which form it is realized, should be more focused in the students' learning instead of, or in addition, to practicalities. Teachers are requiring an insight to students' learning and learning process. This way the studies, and especially learning, as a whole can be improved with the help of course feedback system.

Especially open-ended questions in OCFSs offer the teachers insight into students learning and learning experience. Student's thoughts and learning processes become visible in open-ended questions. Based on the answers in the open-ended questions the teacher can develop courses so that the learning of the student is supported in the best possible way. On the other hand, teachers would like to have different kinds of charts and statistics straight from the OCFS. This is in contradiction with the requirement of open-ended questions. It is very hard for a software to conclude any kind of charts from freely written answers to open-ended questions. However, with careful and continuous development work we think that also this can be possible in future.

The results also indicated that the OCFS should be real-time, so that students could answer to it continuously during their courses. Furthermore, in more general level, continuously during their studies. The possibility to give feedback in real-time would aid the use of OCFS as a tool to make the student's learning visible and this way enhancing teacher's possibilities to guide student's learning experience towards extensive learning. However, at least in TUT, the current OCFS does not technically suit to this kind of continuous real-time giving of feedback. Hence, when the OCFSs are developed, the results of this study must be kept in mind already in the very first

steps of system planning. This feature in OCFSs can be established, if it is recognized already in the beginning of the software development.

One important finding is that the technical platform of an OCFS has to be technically suitable for its purpose, easy to use and compatible with different kinds of mobile devices. Otherwise, the problems of the technical system affect negatively to the student's learning experience.

The answers in this study also highlighted that the students should have training how to give constructive course feedback. This issue is not connected to the feedback system what is used, but to feedback in general. The feedback should be written so that the message is clear for the teachers, e. g. what is working in courses and studies in general, and what is not. Very general feedback does not aid the teachers in developing courses and studies. Furthermore, it does not help the teacher to boost students' learning and learning experience together with the students.

The results of this study show that an OCFS should definitely be something else than it is now in TUT. The definition and planning work of the next OCFS in TUT has already started, and the results of this study are known and recognized in that process. Hopefully the system-to-be will be suitable to support students in their learning, and hopefully the teachers get a more thorough view to students learning experiences with the next OCFS in TUT.

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